

STATE AND LAW

CONSIDERATIONS ON THE POSITION OF THE EUROPEAN COURT OF HUMAN RIGHTS ON THE PRESUMPTION OF INNOCENCE

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the analysis of the position of the European Court of Human Rights on the presumption of innocence.

It is noted that the decisions of the European Court on the presumption of innocence, as a rule, are based on Article 6.2 of the European Convention "On the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms". But there are exceptions. For example, the surprising point is that the issue of illegal evidence is evaluated by the Court on the level of Article 6.1, not Article 6.2 of the Convention. However, the issue in question is directly related to the presumption of innocence.

Referring to the precedent practice of the European Court, the article argues that since "fair trial" is a broad and general concept, after determining whether the presumption of innocence provided for in the second part of Article 6 of the Convention has been violated, any other whether the issues fall within the scope of a "fair trial" should be investigated. However, the European Court's approach to the mentioned issue is completely opposite.

Keywords: the presumption of innocence, European Court of Human Rights, fair trial, guilt, crime.

Although there are a number of international courts in the world (the UN International Court of Justice in The Hague, the African Court of Justice, etc.) position on the presumption of innocence and our considerations about it have not been clarified. There are several reasons for this. First, because the European Court is the first specialized international court established to rule on cases of violated human rights. Therefore, the said court, unlike other international courts, has made more decisions in the field of human rights and has great experience in this field [7, p. 786]. Secondly, since the Court is an international institution that invites member states to change the norms that violate human rights in their internal laws, we believe that the precedent experience of the said court regarding the presumption of innocence is useful for improving the national legislation of our country. It is for these reasons that the position of the European Court on the presumption of innocence is important.

It should be noted that Article 6 of the European Convention "On the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms" (hereinafter - the European Convention) is devoted to the right to a fair trial. That article states: "Everyone has the right to a fair and open investigation of his case within a reasonable time by an independent and impartial court, established on the basis of law, when his civil rights and duties are determined or any criminal charge is brought against him. The court decision shall be made public, but only when it is strictly necessary for reasons of morality, public order or national security in a democratic society, as well as when the interests of minors or the protection of the privacy of the parties require it, or in special cases where, in the opinion of the court, publicity may prejudice the interests of justice the press and the public may not be admitted to the court session during the entire process or a part of it" (first part); "Anyone accused of committing a crime is presumed innocent until proven

guilty according to law" (second part); Anyone charged with a crime has at least the following rights:

(a) to be promptly and fully informed in a language he understands of the nature and grounds of the charge brought against him;

(b) have sufficient time and opportunity to prepare his defence;

(c) to defend himself in person or through counsel of his own choosing, or to avail himself of such defense free of charge when the interests of justice so require, when his funds are insufficient to pay for the services of counsel;

(d) to examine or cause to be examined witnesses who have testified against him and to have the right to call and examine witnesses in his favor under the same conditions as for witnesses who have testified against him;

(e) to use the free assistance of an interpreter if he does not understand or cannot speak the language used in court" (section three).

Apparently, the presumption of innocence is provided for in Article 6.2 of the European Convention, and this right is part of the right to a fair trial.

Khalilov Yunis underlined: "The condition "until proven guilty according to law" reflected in Article 6.2 of the Convention contains an extremely important prohibition: the inadmissibility of using illegal evidence to prove a person's guilt. The Court leaves the question of "proof under the law" to the national law of the States that have ratified the Convention, and it merely examines whether it has been abused" [9].

Decisions of the European Court on the presumption of innocence are, as a rule, based on Article 6.2 of the European Convention. But there are exceptions. For example, it is surprising that the issue related to illegal evidence is evaluated by the Court at the level of Article 6.1, not Article 6.2 of the Convention. However, the issue in question is directly related to the presumption of innocence.

The European Court did not make a specific statement on the relationship between the presumption of innocence provided for in Article 6.2 of the Convention and the right to a fair trial contained in Article 6.1 [6, p. 14]. The Court considers the presumption of innocence provided for in Article 6.2 of the Convention to be a continuation of the right to a fair trial contained in Article 6.1 and a special form of that right (*Deweert v. Belgium* case, paragraphs 56-57). The main view on this point is that the second part of Article 6 of the Convention, together with the third part, is an elaboration of the right to a fair trial in the first part [4, p.404], [6, p.12].

From this point of view, if there is an application regarding the violation of the second part of Article 6 of the Convention, this application may not be considered as a violation of the second part, but it can be evaluated as a violation of the first part. However, the violation of the second part means the violation of the first part as well. According to Schroeder, the right in the second part together with the third part constitutes the core and basis of "fair trial".

In our opinion, since "fair trial" is a broad and general concept, after determining whether the presumption of innocence stipulated in the second part has been violated, what other issues are included in the scope of "fair trial" entry should be investigated. However, the European Court's approach to the mentioned issue is completely opposite. Contrary to the position of that court, for example, in Germany, if it is determined that there is no violation after first examining whether the second part has been violated, then the issue of whether the first part has been violated is examined. We believe that the European Court should first examine whether the second part has been violated, and after concluding that the second part has not been violated, the question of whether the first part has been violated should be investigated. Because the second part is considered a special norm in relation to the first part.

In the experience of the European Court, the scope of application of the presumption of innocence covers the justice carried out on acts considered criminal. In other words, this right applies to accused persons accused of committing a crime.

However, the Court noted in *Albert and Le Compte v. Belgium* (10 February 1983) that the clause also applied to certain types of civil cases that could be considered "criminal cases" under the Convention, such as professional disciplinary proceedings [5, p. 76].

It should be noted that for the application of the presumption of innocence, it is not necessary to initiate a criminal case. The European Court gives an autonomous definition to "criminal charge" and considers the definition based on national law to be of relative value only. The position of the Court is that for the purposes of paragraph 1 of Article 6 of the Convention, the official notification of a person by a competent state authority about the existence of the possibility of committing a crime is considered an "accusation" and the presumption of innocence applies to the person from the moment of receiving this information.

The European Court stated in the case *Eckle v. Germany* (1982) that in addition to formally informing a person of the possibility of a crime being committed,

other procedures and measures that significantly affect the situation of the suspect can also be considered "accusations".

In addition, requiring the authorities investigating customs crimes to provide evidence and freeze the bank account (*Funke v. France* case), as well as providing the person with a lawyer before the initial stage of the investigation (*Angelucci v. Italy* case), regarding the deputy and in one case, the prosecutor's request to waive his right to immunity ("*Frau v. Italy*" case) was accepted as a "criminal charge" by the European Court.

In the cases "*Engel and others v. the Netherlands*" and "*König v. Germany*" the Court stated that "criminal charge" is an autonomous concept, the position of the Court is not related to the approach of this concept in the domestic laws of countries ("*Engel and others v. the Netherlands*" on June 8, 1976 paragraphs 81-82 of the decision dated 28 June 1978 in the case "*König v. Germany*", paragraphs 88-89).

In this regard, states are free to consider a specific act as a crime. An act that is considered a crime under the domestic legislation of the states is also considered a crime during the application of the Convention. However, an act that is not considered a crime in domestic legislation, for example, an act that creates disciplinary liability, may be considered a criminal act during the application of the Convention and fall under the influence of Article 6 [1, p. 248], [3, p. 83]. In this way, the European Court prevents the party states from evading the guarantees in Article 6 of the Convention. Of course, there are no uniform criteria and dimensions accepted in the international arena for which actions are considered criminal or actions that lead to disciplinary liability. Nevertheless, the European Court, which does not want to leave the guaranteeing of guarantees in Article 6 of the Convention to the discretion of the party states, has defined the criteria for the mentioned issue. Thus, the Court in its decision on the case "*Engel et al. v. the Netherlands*" as well as in subsequent decisions further improved the specific criteria and defined three criteria when deciding whether or not a person accused of committing a crime within the framework of Article 6 of the Convention should be considered: I. Nationality of the act legal description; II. The nature of the crime or the nature of the act; III. The nature and severity of the sanction to which the interested person may be subjected. (Paragraphs 82-83 of the judgment of 08 June 1976 in the case of "*Engel and others v. The Netherlands*"; paragraphs 33-35 of the judgment of 23 March 1994 in the case of "*Ravnsborg v. Sweden*") [1, p. 248], [3, p. 99].

It is not necessary to have all three criteria together at the same time. The evaluation of one of them is sufficient in terms of ensuring Article 6 of the Convention. However, in many cases, the criteria in points "b" and "c" are taken together as a whole [2, p. 409].

Thus, in some cases, the Court considers even a disciplinary offense as a criminal charge, even if it is not considered a crime under the criminal law, and examines it within the scope of Article 6 of the Convention.

Apparently, the scope of application of the presumption of innocence has been expanded by the Court [3, p. 84], [8, p. 46].

Summarizing what we have said, we can conclude that Article 6.2 of the European Convention contains a provision on the presumption of innocence, and this right is part of the right to a fair trial. Decisions of the European Court on the presumption of innocence have extremely important legal value.

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